
INFLUENCE OF LEADERSHIP STYLES ON EMPLOYEE ENGAGEMENT

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Abstract

Although sustaining employee engagement in the workplace can be challenging for business executives, doing so is essential to an organization's financial success. This theoretical exercise set out to investigate the methods employed by corporate executives to deal with or lessen the effects of employee disengagement. The method examined effective employee engagement tactics used by company executives, such as training. The study's conclusions demonstrate that employee happiness is more influenced by transformational, transactional and laissez faire leadership styles than by employee motivation, which affects employee engagement. While teamwork excels when working with a transactional leader, employees led by transformational leaders have the highest levels of satisfaction with their jobs, leadership style, and organizational structure. Lastly, the laissez-faire leadership style is common in project-related businesses because it promotes employee autonomy and empowerment in decision-making, both of which raise employee engagement. There is a moderating effect of sub-unit culture over organizational culture on the link between employee engagement and leadership style.

Keywords: Employee Engagement, Training, Transformational, Transactional, Laissez Faire, Organizational Culture, Satisfaction, Motivation

1. Introduction

Generally speaking, within the last ten years, research on leadership has grown significantly. Research studies have predominantly examined transformational, transactional and laissez faire leadership styles (Bass and Avolio, 1993; Hassi, 2018), as these approaches have been demonstrated to be highly effective in enhancing leaders' effectiveness.

In this instance, leaders are able to energise, motivate, and inspire their staff to accomplish the desired goals (Andersen, 2016). A number of academics have approached the topic of leadership from the perspective of how their actions affect their followers. Previous research has shown that leadership affects employee work outcomes, such as satisfaction, commitment, citizenship behaviors, and innovation (Alkahtani, 2015; Chandra and Priyono, 2016; Haghghi and Maleki, 2016; Hassi, 2018; Le and Lei, 2017; Walumbwa et al., 2005; Yao et al., 2014; Yıldız et al., 2014 cited in Aboramadan and Dahleez, 2020). More specifically, transformational, transactional and laissez faire leadership were found to influence employees' attitudes and behaviours, especially through training culminating employee engagement.

The functions of the leaders were covered in a few literary works, (Cornforth, 2014; Parsehyan, 2017). For example, despite extensive Business leaders face extremely complex managerial tasks and responsibilities, including limited resources and unclear work environments, as evidenced by the growing significance of these organizations (Fowler, 2013b; Lewis, 2001 cited in Aboramadan and Dahleez, 2020). This suggests that business leaders must possess the skills and qualities typically associated with managers. Leaders in these organizations must possess strong managerial skills, personal integrity, vision, and desire in order to collaborate with volunteers and employees in a successful manner.

According to Birasnav (2014, cited in Aboramadan and Dahleez, 2020), leadership is perceived as an interpersonal impact that happens via a communication system with the aim of accomplishing the objectives of the business. Additionally, prior research has shown that leadership can have an impact on companies and people, which may be observed from a good leader who can persuade the followers to act in a way that fosters favorable results for the company. Moreover, these executives add more positive effects to the workplace than any other employee in the company (Gibson et al., 1991). Thus, it is imperative for an organization to have leadership that can impact workers' productivity, happiness, and effectiveness (Turner and Muller, 2005) as well as foster favorable employee attitudes.

Discussion in the corporate sector, business organizations neglected to address the transformational-transactional leadership stream (Rowold and Rohman, 2009). Additionally, rather than focusing on specific leadership philosophies, the majority of organizational leadership research projects primarily examined boards (Hailey, 2006).

There have been a number of recent initiatives to expand on the leadership research across board. For example, some researchers looked at the instrumental and participative styles of leadership and how they affected workers' work engagement in Italian social cooperatives (Sarti, 2014); the effect of transformational leaders on the culture of organizations and the effectiveness of nongovernmental organizations in India (Shiva and Suar, 2012); the effect of transformational leadership on innovation and culture in American nonprofit organizations (Jaskyte, 2004); and the effect of servant leadership on organizational commitment and organizational citizenship behavior in Italian profits and nongovernmental organizations (Bobbio et al., 2012).

Despite the large body of empirical research on leaders-followers' work-related attitudes and behaviors in the private sector, a number of studies (Hailey, 2006; Park et al., 2018; Rowold and Rohman, 2009) have offered recommendations for additional research on the critical role of leadership in leader-follower interactions in non-profit organizations (e.g. Aboramadan et al., 2020). Additionally, little is known about how leadership affects workers' outcomes connected to their jobs in most organizations (Park et al., 2018). Consequently, more empirical research is needed to investigate how leadership influences workers' attitudes and behaviors. Overall, although being studied in business research, the impact of job engagement has not received

enough attention as a moderating factor in the relationship between employee outcomes and leadership in nonprofit organizations (Park et al., 2018). Regarding NPOs, the purpose of this research is to look into the effects of three types of leadership in these organizations: transformational, transactional and laissez faire leadership, on the affective commitment and OCB of workers. This article offers a number of perspectives on the significance of employee training engagement taking into cognizance the prevailing effect of leadership styles in the organizations.

2.0 Literature Review

The fast-changing environment, complexity, economic unrest, unstable business workplaces and globalization that organizations—including nonprofits—are currently facing have drawn the attention of HR professionals to the significance of leadership in organizations, as it affects service quality, employee retention, and overall business performance (Barling et al., 1996; Parry and Sinha, 2005; Sirianni and Frey, 2001). Without a question, in these uncertain times, the ability to lead a company's most valuable asset—its human capital, or better known as the "employee"—has grown.

Employers and executives want their workforces to be engaged, and they invest a lot of time and money especially in employee training in making this happen. Engaged workforces have a significant impact on worker productivity and organizational performance. Not much study has been done on the impact of leadership on employee engagement across industries, notwithstanding earlier studies conducted in other areas.

The area of employee engagement has several large knowledge gaps. As a result, the employee participation research has both academic and practical implications for increasing knowledge of employee training engagement and the role of leadership techniques in motivating. Conversely, it's vital to look into how employees view leadership styles and how they affect their training engagement. Because this leadership may either facilitate or obstruct involvement, it depends on the leader's style and actions. The relationship between management and employees, on the other hand, has gotten less attention in the literature. Leadership and employee engagement has been investigated and the transformational leaders found as the most effective methods for boosting employee training engagement.

Because of the ongoing changes and difficulties that nonprofit organizations confront, researchers and academics have been increasingly interested in the topic of leadership in these organizations. In the current period of constrained financial and human resources, coupled with a dynamic work environment, non-profit executives must exercise their positions in novel and creative ways in order to accomplish the organization's goals. Golensky (2011)

When compared to their peers in businesses and governments, NPO staff are typically underpaid (Bittschi et al., 2015). This would lead to a distortion of the workers' sense of appreciation and a decrease in their level of involvement at work (Hulkko-Nyman et al., 2012). As a result, NPO leaders are crucial in guaranteeing favorable workplace results because of their ongoing efforts to improve worker commitment (Vecina et al., 2013), job engagement (Park et al., 2018), and performance (Erdurmazli, 2019).

2.1 Therotical Review

2.1.1 Conceptional Framework

Figure 2.1

Research (2024)

2.2 Leadership Styles

Perceived as a pattern of influencing people's behaviors, leadership style (Zigarmi et al., 2004). Various leadership styles have been examined in earlier research, and Woods and King's (2012) study discovered that transformational, transactional and laissez faire leadership were the most often studied forms.

2.3 Leadership Theories

Leadership is underpinned by various theories as shown below in figure 2.1. Leadership theories can be categorized into four main schools namely, the Trait approach, Behavioural approach, Contingency approach and the Full Range approach.

Figure 2.2 Basic Leadership Approaches

Adapted from Wendy Oliver (2012)

Fundamentally, these can be highlighted thus:

2.3.1 Trait Theory:

The trait theory is referred to in most writings as the original method of researching leadership. According to the trait school of thought, leaders are not created; they are born. Physical, social, and psychological traits that are innate in some people, according to Bass (1981), are what eventually distinguish leaders from non-leaders.

2.3.2 Behaviourial Theory:

After abandoning the trait approach, the next major shift in leadership focused on analyzing the kinds of behaviors leaders displayed in an effort to evaluate effective leadership. This method focused on the behavior of the leader rather than their appearance or potential personality features in an effort to ascertain what makes a good leader (Greenberg, 1999). According to the behavioural approach theory, most people may become effective leaders if they adopt the behaviours of great leaders since behaviours are easier to acquire than qualities (Greenberg, 1999; Northouse, 2004). Blake & Mouton (1964), the University of Michigan and Ohio State models (Hellriegel, Jackson et al., 2004), and the Theory X and Theory Y model (McGregor, 1960) are the three primary behavioral models.

2.3.3 Contingency Theory:

The next fundamental step in leadership was the contingency method, which described how leaders are matched with suitable circumstances. By examining the leader in light of the circumstances surrounding their work, the contingency method marked a change in leadership research (Fiedler, 1978). Thus, this theory postulated that a crucial element in deciding the degree of success or failure with relation to leadership behavior was the situation. Put differently, this idea proposed that comprehension of the context in which leaders led was necessary to evaluate their performance (Fiedler, 1978).

Fiedler's contingency model, Hersey and Blanchard's situational leadership model, House's path-goal model, and the Leader-Member Exchange theory were the four main contingency models that were postulated.

2.4 Full Range Leadership Approach

Research could not agree upon the optimum way for leaders to influence their followers in light of the aforementioned theories. As a result, a new theory known as the Full Range Leadership Approach eventually emerged and is currently acknowledged as the most effective leadership style in 21st-century organizations (Bass & Riggio, 2006). Three dimensions of leadership are covered by this theory: transactional, transformational, and laissez-faire leadership styles. This theory's basic tenet is that all leaders will exhibit elements of each style to some extent, but whether a leader has a transformational, transactional, or laissez-faire style of leadership will depend on how frequently they exhibit particular leadership behaviors.

2.4.1 Transformational Leadership

To be more precise, transformational leaders are those who are followed by their followers in order to accomplish the goals of the organization; this phenomenon is demonstrated by the followers' respect and trust for the leader (Bass, 1985). In the meantime, it has been determined that charm, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, personalized concern, and personal recognition are the components that make up transformative leadership.

According to Riggio (2009), charisma is a group of personality attributes that causes leaders to have an impact on people's emotions and behaviors. This component has been seen as crucial to building trust and respect (Bealer and Bhanugopan, 2014). On the other hand, inspiring motivation describes a leader's capacity to inspire others, create confidence in their followers, and present a compelling vision for them (Bass, 1985; Bass and Bass, 2008).

Furthermore, the degree to which leaders develop their followers' capacity for critical thought and problem-solving is referred to as intellectual stimulation (Bass, 1985). Individualized attention, the fourth element of transformation leadership, focuses on the leaders' responsibility in coaching and mentoring their followers in order to help them reach their full potential through educational opportunities (Avolio et al., 1999; Bass and Riggio, 2006). Conversely, personal recognition is concerned with leaders praising workers' accomplishments and rewarding the worthy workers (Rafferty and Griffin, 2004).

There is empirical research that shows how transformational leadership improves both the organization and its members. Previous research has shown that transformational leadership significantly predicts a number of outcomes, including high performance (Jing, 2018), job satisfaction (Aydogmus et al., 2018; Spitzbart, 2013), trust in leaders (Holtz and Harold, 2008), motivation (Charbonneau et al., 2001), team learning (Bucic et al., 2010), and innovation (Boerner et al., 2007).

2.4.2 Transactional Leadership

In addition, the concept of transactional leadership holds that the boss establishes the standards that the staff members must adhere to (Bass, 1985; Kanungo, 2001). As a result, this style of leadership is more closely linked to preserving the orderly operation of the company. In order to foster subordinate loyalty, lessen resistance, and promote accomplishments based on rewards, transactional leaders must also define positions, create targets, and ascertain the prerequisites of the task (Deichmann and Stam, 2015).

There are two components to the transactional leadership style: management by exception and contingent compensation. To be more precise, the contingent incentive is predicated mostly on the idea that managers assign tasks and anticipate that workers will receive rewards based on their accomplishments (Antonakis et al., 2003). In this instance, there is a motivation-based agreement between the followers and the leader about rewards and penalties. Put differently, transactional

leaders set goals for their staff to meet and offer rewards for doing so. When management by exception is used, leaders monitor the performance of their subordinates and intervene when significant deviations occur. The relationship between transactional leadership and organizational effectiveness (Bass and Riggio, 2006), organizational commitment (Jabeen et al., 2015), and job satisfaction (Clabaugh et al., 2000; Epitropaki and Martin, 2005; Spitzbart, 2013) is supported by the literature on leadership. Lastly, social exchange theory provides a solid theoretical foundation for our understanding of the relationships between transformational-transactional leadership and workers' attitudes and behaviors (Blau, 1964). Expanding upon this notion, we may contend that a reciprocal relationship exists between the leader and the following. For example, followers are more likely to respond positively by exhibiting good attitudes and actions if they believe the transformational leader is encouraging them and personally recognizes their potential. Similarly, followers will be inspired to repay their transactional leader by exhibiting positive attitudes and actions connected to work if they believe that they are fair. On the other hand, Zhang and colleagues (2014) argued that there is no significant correlation between transactional leadership and employee engagement. Zhang et al. came to the conclusion that this was due to the traits of transactional leaders, who depend on receiving something in return for doing the assignment.

2.4.3 Laissez Faire Leadership

With a laissez-faire leadership style, there are no agreements or transactions between the leader and followers, in contrast to transformational and transactional leadership (Bass 1985a; Bass & Avolio 1993). As a result, there is no presence of a leadership act. According to Robbins, Decenzo, and Coulter (2010), followers are completely free to decide how to proceed and complete tasks. According to a few studies, in certain industries such as healthcare, pharmaceutical research and development, architecture and engineering, and product design—where workers are subject matter experts and make the best decisions and advisors—laissez-faire leadership is the most effective style of leadership (Leahey 2014; Birn 2014).

2.5 Employee Engagement

Employees in any organization vary widely in terms of how engaged they are at work and how much effort and focus they put into their work. Over the past 20 years, employee involvement has emerged as a relatively new construct (Rafferty, Maben, West & Robinson, 2005). It is a broad construct lacking a single, widely accepted definition, but this is neither exceptional nor problematic given that many other psychological constructs have had a similar lack of clarity from the outset when it comes to their engagement with the social sciences (Macey & Schneider, 2008). The study of engagement in work environments has grown in importance as a research topic as a result of the growing trend towards "positive psychology," which emphasizes human strengths and optimal functioning rather than flaws and malfunctions (Macey & Schneider, 2008). Divergent perspectives exist on the conceptualization of work engagement, despite the consensus among academics regarding its existence (Bakker, Schaufeli et al., 2008). Nonetheless, the majority of them concur that prior ideas like work satisfaction, employee commitment, and organizational citizenship behavior are where employee engagement first emerged (Robinson, Perryman & Hayday, 2004). While these ideas are related to and encompassed within it, employee engagement has a wider reach and can be defined in a number of ways.

Employees that are engaged are totally focused on their work and will work very hard to make the organization successful because they are concerned about the company's future (Seijts & Crim, 2006). It has also been defined by others as a person who is completely absorbed in and excited about their work, as well as a person's happiness and excitement for their work (Harter & Schmidt, 2008).

Researchers refer to engagement using a variety of terminology that can be used interchangeably, such as employee, work, personal, and job engagement (Anitha, 2014).

Employee motivation, according to Wollard and Shuck (2011), is a personal factor that precedes employee engagement. There are other content- and process-based theories of motivation; however, the Path-Goal Theory, which links various leadership philosophies, will be the focus of this discussion (Bass and Avolio, 1997). Employee engagement and motivation have been proven to be correlated (Kahn 1990; May, Gilson & Harter 2004; Christian, Garza & Slaughter 2011).

The conceptual framework for this study was developed on the basis of the notion of employee engagement. We made use of Kahn's (1990) employee engagement theory to comprehend the methods employed by company executives to include their workforce. Workplace productivity levels can be impacted by employee engagement (Anitha, 2014). From a behavioral perspective of organizational commitment and performance, engagement theory aids in the explanation of the factors that lead to and hinder employee engagement. Kahn's theory states that motivated workers express themselves viscerally, emotionally, and cognitively when engaged in safe, purposeful activities and when they are aware that resources are accessible to finish the tasks (Kahn, 1990).

High levels of wellbeing are experienced by emotionally invested workers (Kahn, 1990). According to Kumar and Pansari (2015), physically engaged workers exhibit high levels of productivity, and intellectually engaged workers view their work as meaningful. Emotional and cognitive involvement are necessary for physical engagement (Shuck & Reio, 2014). Employees that are engaged show dedication, give their all, are creative, and consider expenses, quality, customer service, and safety (Kahn, 1990).

When workers physically, mentally, and emotionally disengage from their task, it is known as disengagement (Kahn, 1990). A company's ability to achieve its strategic goals depends on its ability to engage its workforce, which it does by providing the tools, resources, and atmosphere needed for both effective leadership and productive workers (Anitha, 2014).

Basically, employee training engagement help drive employee engagement by creating and maintaining a positive and growth oriented environment for employees where open communication is encouraged and modeled. Taylor (1949) cited in Okeah (2020) was the father of scientific management and task processes and procedures were the guiding principles; hence the importance of employees training was highlighted. So, the training of the employees in the relevant skills will ever encourage and get such involved and engaged in the organization and result to optimal performance. In this case, more than the others, the transformational leaders who have the interests of the employees will suffice and conventionally encourage engaged employees through periodic training and development. In the light of this, the transactional leaders to achieve the organizational goals ought to take the issue of training serious: as that will help the organization by encouraging the employees to be totally involved and committed to it and it's set goals, The laissez- faire leaders which are mostly found in some unique industries like health, pharmaceutical etc will normally leave the employees to their professional training and demands; as they are mostly considered to be perfection-specific and therefore involved with the organization. The importance of employee training to leaders who desire increased productivity, cannot be over-emphasised. It has equally helped to motivate and bring satisfaction to employees and thereby develop organization citizen behaviours among the employees. Such employee 'work with and not for' the organization; having been fully internalized; through engagement.

Transformational leaders because of their general disposition on the well-being of the employees will significantly do well in ensuring that they are properly trained and by so doing, they find relevancy and needs to stay with the organization with devotion and profound commitment to contribute to its' success. Nevertheless, the transactional leader as the last resort will sparingly train the employees, being cost expert. The laissez faire leader is

an easy going leader and considers the feeling, freedom and the independence of the employees and would not be a hindrance to their trainings. Accordingly, all of these styles of leadership contribute to motivate, satisfy and encourage employees in various degrees, to be engaged with the organization, orchestrated by the training opportunities.

Amah, (2016) posits that the objectives of training and development include increased productivity, adaption to technological changes, fulfillment of social responsibilities, employee motivation and satisfaction. Training benefits both the organization and the employees which culminate to deep commitment and being fully engrossed in the organizations values and set goal. Amah, (2016) further affirms that when employees know how to efficiently and safely carry out their tasks, they are satisfied, with their work and will want to be at it often. Which other way can they have mastery if not through training facilitated by a leader? So, employee training is panacea to employee engagement empowerment and for an organization to build what we term utility employees. Therefore, leaders should engender employee training as that will be of immense benefits and lead to fruitful employee engagement.

2.5.1 Employee Motivation

Vroom (1964) as cited in Grant (2019) proposed that, based on the outcomes of his expectancy theory, motivation is the product of expectancy and expectancy is the effort that results in a desired level of performance. This is in opposition to Kahn's (1990) employee engagement theory.

Using the expectancy theory, Van De Voorde (2016) as cited in Grant (2019), investigated workplace motivation and discovered that higher levels of engagement were present when people understood and fulfilled expectations. Workers who are not aware of the goals of the company or who are under a lot of pressure to succeed may be less inclined to put in the effort necessary to complete a task, which could lead to a decline in engagement (Van De Voorde et al., 2016, cited in Grant, 2019). Job involvement and trust are the main determinants of organizational effectiveness and trust creates employee motivation (Nasomboon, 2014, cited in Grant, 2019). Organizations must be an environment in which leaders can express their expectations and identify clear objectives for employees (Karanges, et al., 2015). Organizations that meet employee expectations influence employee motivation (Imran, et al., 2014, as cited in Grant, 2019). Similar to Van De Voorde, Van Veldhoven, and Veld (2016), Imran et al. (2014) noted that organizations experience higher levels of engagement and productivity when people know what is expected of them and meet those expectations. Employee engagement, motivation, and productivity may all suffer from leaders who are unable to set clear goals for their team members (Imran et al., 2014, cited in Grant, 2019). According to Vroom (1964), the expectation theory demonstrated that: (a) an individual's effort and performance were correlated; (b) excellent performance produced a positive return; (c) the return satisfied an individual's need; and (d) the desire to satisfy an individual's need justified the effort. The expectancy hypothesis is based on expectation, instrumentality, and valence. Expectancy refers to a person's confidence and ability, valence is the emotional reactions people have to results, and instrumentality indicates that the reward corresponds to the labor undertaken (Vroom, 1964; Purvis, Zagenczyk, & McCray, 2015). Ferinia, Yuniarsi, and Disman (2016) found support for Vroom's theory and pointed out that a relationship between personal effort, performance, and awards that could lead to employee satisfaction and engagement. Ernst (2014), cited in Grant, (2019) pointed out that the expectancy theory is predicated on four assumptions. The first presumption is that people enter organizations with preconceived notions about their needs, motives, and past experiences. The second is that a person's actions

are deliberate (a conscious decision). The third is that various people have different expectations of their employers, including opportunities for growth, competitive pay, and job stability. The fourth is that people will consider other options to improve their own results (Ernst, 2014, cited in Grant, 2019).

When people think that the following three things will happen, they will get motivated: (a) effort will result in an acceptable performance; (b) prizes will follow performance; and (c) the rewards will have a good value (Nimri, Bdair, & Bitar, 2015). These components define valence, instrumentality, and expectancy. When developing and implementing ways to engage and encourage employees, managers need to make sure that all three aspects are present (Nimri et al., 2015). This study is consistent with expectation theory, which holds that higher expectancies and positive valence and instrumentality promote employee engagement (Nimri et al., 2015, cited in Grant, 2019).

Given that many firms do not link rewards to performance, the expectation theory may not be sufficient (Barron & Hulleman, 2015, cited in Grant, 2019). Employee engagement may also be impacted by other factors including (a) position, (b) effort, (c) responsibility, and (d) education, among others. Thus, it makes sense to take into account different leadership philosophies, techniques for inspiring others, and other theories in order to increase employee engagement in a company.

2.5.2 Employee Satisfaction

High positive relationships between employee engagement and satisfaction, as determined by productivity, profit, employee turnover, and customer satisfaction indices, were found in a study by Harter, Schmidt, and Hayes (2002). According to theorists Likert (1961) and McGregor (1960), contented workers are productive workers.

2.5.3 Organization Citizenship Behaviour

The term "organizational citizenship behavior" (OCB) describes the extra-role activities that workers do outside of the workplace that advance the goals of the business. Since these are voluntarily performed by employees at their own discretion, the organization's rewarding program may not always acknowledge them (Humphrey, 2012, cited in Aboramadan & Dahleez, 2020). Notably, OCB promotes the employees' job performance by supporting psychological and social work that is maintained and encouraged (Organ, 1997, cited in Aboramadam & Dahleez, 2020). Additionally, it was discovered that OCB helped to increase social capital and the organization's general effectiveness (Bolino et al., 2002; Nielsen et al., 2012; Podsakoff et al., 2014, cited in Aboramadan & Dahleez, 2020). It was theorized that transformational leadership plays a significant role in promoting OCB, allowing transformational leaders to motivate their subordinates to perform beyond their jobs and to challenge work complexities.

Nonetheless, it is evident that transactional leadership is crucial to the advancement of OCB. Given that followers' decisions to participate in OCB actions are mostly based on their perceptions of potential incentives and rewards, it is possible that contingent reward behaviors and followers' OCB are related (Barbuto and Story, 2011).

2.6 Organizational Culture

The effect of leadership style and organizational culture on work satisfaction was examined by Lok and Crawford (2003). Employee behavior and decision-making are influenced by organizational culture, which also indirectly affects workers (Berson, Oreg & Dvir 2008;

Giberson et al. 2009). Research has demonstrated that organizational culture has a significant impact on leadership and that the two are closely related (Berson, Oreg & Dvir 2008; Giberson et al. 2009; Sharma, S. K. & Sharma, A. 2010). Additionally, studies have argued that an organization's subculture is more prevalent than its primary culture and has a greater impact on its workforce (Bloor and Dawson, 1994). Workers can more easily relate to the unit's subculture than the organization's overall culture (Prestholdt, Lane, & Mathews 1987). It is claimed that leaders are the ones that shape the culture within their organization (Mintzberg 2013). Leaders create subcultures by modeling behavior, values, and advice. Research showed that employees identify more with a subculture that is shaped by their leaders; as a result, the subculture of the organization affects employee loyalty and attitude (Lok, Westwood & Crawford 2005).

3.0 Findings

The study's findings are significant because they can help corporate executives identify effective employee engagement tactics. It has been shown by researchers that disengaged employees are less productive than engaged employees (Bedarkar & Pandita, 2014), and that there is a substantial positive association between an organization's ability to produce high-quality results with employee engagement (Guaspari, 2015). This is necessitated by high inputs of training offered to the employees. Scholars (Grant, 2019), have additionally observed the deficiencies in the literature about employee engagement, particularly with leadership and employee training engagement, indicating the necessity for more in-depth qualitative studies on the topic (Kaliannan & Adjovu, 2015; Shuck & Reio, 2014)

If company leaders want to succeed, they need to know how employee engagement affects the workplace. Enhancing employee engagement tactics through training raises productivity and engagement levels, which helps the company meet its goals and objectives (Alagaraja & Shuck, 2015). Examining tactics (training) that could influence worker participation could provide company executives with knowledge about regulations that could increase output and profitability.

4.0 Conclusion

Although leaders claim to practice transactional leadership, there is a good chance that their style may combine elements of the three transformational, transactional and laissez faire leadership because leaders have had to adapt their style in response to a variety of factors, including the state of the organization, tasks within it, the seniority, capabilities, and diversity of their workforce as well as the level of empowerment exercised and the guidance that employees require.

Psychological meaningfulness is a means by which leaders can positively influence workers' sense of worth within the company; training and development help to make this happen (Basit & Arshad, 2016). Scholars further affirm that leaders need to make sure the required resources are available and support the achievement of personal goals and ambitions if the objective is to motivate employees to engage. They stated that professional development, training opportunities, and other programs could positively affect employee engagement. In the same way, Fletcher (2016) noted that to encourage participation among people of the organization, leaders focus on personal, professional, and organizational growth, through training to enhance efficiency, effectiveness and employee confidence building.

The principle of employee engagement to highlight the tactics company executives can utilize to motivate their staff members and ensure that they are productive and beneficial to the company and to the employees and become fully involved with and in the organization remain most evident.

Therefore, the importance of leadership to buy-in through training and strengthen the workforce, to the point of being engaged or involved is the objective of this and can be meaningfully achieved via the established leadership styles at various degrees of attainment. However, the superior position of transformational leadership above others remains a truism. The avenues through which training should be deployed to achieve sustainable and fruitful employment engagement with substantial contributions of the other styles of leadership should not be taken for granted.

5.0 Recommendations

The need for more research on transformational leadership, transactional leadership and laissez faire leadership and its relationship to enhancing and motivating employee engagement in order to reach the best production environment that contributes to achieving the goals of the organizations regarding employee training engagement remain a dynamic one. This research is an attempt to enrich organizations with research-based information in terms of leadership styles and its impact on employee training engagement.

It has been discovered that these forms of leadership influence how motivated workers are. The research did find that transformative leadership is more indicative of employee training engagement, though, so the suggestions that follow could be useful for the organizations goals attainment.

-Managers and supervisors should consider undergoing transformational leadership training as it will improve their ability to inspire, motivate, and involve their team members and advance the overall performance of their particular business units.

-Researcher recommends a development of an annual training program from the human resources department concerned with developing comprehensive leadership and attracting and developing distinguished leaders, which may affect the performance results of organization and government agencies and contribute to the high rates of employee engagement

-Leadership mentorship programs that provide managers with ongoing developmental feedback on their behaviors and how they could link to the ideal traits that generate effective and proactive transformational leadership behavior could be an addition to the formal education of leaders (Dibley, 2009; cited in Majrashi, 2022).

-The long-term viability of organizations, as well as succession planning, are constantly at risk unless leaders of those institutions feel that part of their responsibility as leaders is to develop their employees to assume leadership responsibilities. Additionally, leaders ought to think about implementing transformational leadership philosophies, which studies have shown to be the most engagement-friendly leadership philosophies.

6.0 Recommendation for Further Studies

It is necessary to conduct further research on the interactions between many factors and the effects of leadership styles on employee engagement, such as performance reviews. The effects of other leadership styles like authentic, servant leadership equally deserve further investigations.

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